

Information sheet 1.07

Use of non-contaminated water

This information sheet is a supporting document to Appendix A ('Standardised checklist of risk reduction options') of the Guidance of the EFSA Plant Health Panel on quantitative pest risk assessment

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A. Description of the RRO

The use, in particular for the field irrigation, of water from rivers or ditches may in some cases have as a consequence the occurrence of different problems including phytotoxicity for the presence of chemicals, load of organic matter and increase of pest populations. Indeed, a wide range of plant pathogens, as well as algae and equipment clogging biofilms, have been identified in irrigation water sources and distribution systems (Adin and Sacks, 1991; Camberato & Lopez, 2010; Dehghanisani et al., 2005; Hong & Moorman, 2005; Juanico et al., 1995; Raudales et al., 2014; Ristaino & Gumpertz, 2000; Yan et al., 2009). Plant pathogens producing motile spores (zoospores) such as the oomycetes *Pythium* spp. and *Phytophthora* spp. may be freely present in water, whereas those that do not produce swimming structures (e.g., *Rhizoctonia solani* and *Thielaviopsis basicola*) may be carried by bulk flow with soil debris in the water (Baker & Matkin, 1978). Remarkably, these microorganisms may be present when downstream plots are irrigated with the exceeding water collected from other contaminated plots. Several water treatments including chemical (chlorine, bromine, chlorine dioxide, ionized copper, copper salts, ionized silver, ozone, hydrogen peroxide, and peroxyacetic acid), physical control (filtration, heat, and ultraviolet radiation), and ecological (slow sand filtration, biosurfactants and constructed wetlands) can be applied to eliminate these waterborne microorganisms. Raudales et al., (2014) provide an extensive review of these methods and conclude that improved overall system design is required for correct management of these waterborne microbes, including a multiple barrier approach combining pre-filtration, multiple treatment stages, and monitoring of water quality as it affects disinfection strength of these treatments (Copes et al., 2004; Huang et al., 2011). When water decontamination is not feasible and, in particular, in open fields the prevention of pest introduction or spread is achieved banning the use of water sources from probably contaminated rivers or ditches and ensuring, when feasible, the hydric isolation of plots. These situations may occur for instance in regions where *Ralstonia solanacearum* is known to be present.

Tap water in the EU would fulfil the criteria of pest-free water and this is an option that may be interesting for medium-small farms producing high value added crops (e.g., ornamentals).

Below some details on the different water treatments are given.

- **Chemical treatments:**

Chlorine can be applied to irrigation water as a gas (Cl_2); as a liquid, mainly as either sodium hypochlorite (NaOCl) or purified hypochlorous acid (HOCl); or as a solid, most commonly as calcium hypochlorite ($\text{Ca}(\text{ClO})_2$). A dosage rate of 2mg l^{-1} of free chlorine, which is typically used in irrigation (Fisher et al., 2008a,b), produced high mortality of oomycete zoospores (Hong et al., 2003; Lang et al., 2008). In contrast, mortality of mycelia and sporangia of oomycetes required 4 mg l^{-1} with 0.5 and 8 min contact

time, respectively (Hong et al., 2003). *Fusarium oxysporum* and *R. solani* required 8 mg l⁻¹ with 5 min contact time and 10 mg l⁻¹ with 10 min contact time to achieve mortality higher than 90%, respectively (Cayanan et al., 2009). The concentration required to control bacterial pathogens ranged from 0.1 to 4 mg l⁻¹ (Poncet et al., 2001; Robbs et al., 1995; Roberts and Muchovej, 2009; Thompson, 1965). Between 5 and 30 mg l⁻¹ controlled algae in studies by Chase and Conover (1993) and Rav-Acha et al. (1995). Commercial greenhouse recycled irrigation water treated with 4 mg l⁻¹ of chlorine (applied as sodium hypochlorite) with 30 min contact time completely eliminated Cucumber leaf spot virus (CLSV) inoculum, but 3 mg l⁻¹ had no effect on virus viability (Rosner et al., 2006). Nematodes are highly resistant to chlorination (Grech and Rijkenberg, 1991; Stanton and O'Donnell, 1994). Bacteria attached to biofilm surfaces are much more resistant to chlorination than free bacteria (Bois et al., 1997; LeChevallier et al., 1988). Treatment with 1 or 3 mg l⁻¹ of chlorine resulted in 99.7 or 99.9% survival of bacteria within biofilms, respectively (Bois et al., 1997).

Chlorine dioxide, unlike chlorine gas, does not hydrolyze in water and remains as a dissolved gas (Amy et al., 2000). The effective dose of this chemical ranged from 0.5 mg l⁻¹ with 2 min contact time for *F. oxysporum* conidia (Mebalds et al., 1995) to an estimated dose of 57 mg l⁻¹ for *T. basicola* conidia (Copes et al., 2004). Growers typically target about 0.25 mg mg l⁻¹ residual concentration at the emitter for continuous injection and 20–50 mg mg l⁻¹ for shock treatment to eliminate biofilms (Fisher et al., 2008c).

Ozone is an unstable gas which must be generated onsite, typically via corona discharge or ultraviolet radiation (Degrémont, 1979; US-EPA, 1999). A residual dose under 1 mg l⁻¹ is typically suggested for greenhouse irrigation (Hayes et al., 2009), and this can effectively control different bacteria, fungi and oomycetes (Raudales et al., 2014). However, viruses can require much higher doses, up to 100 mg l⁻¹ with 30 min contact time (e.g., Tomato mosaic virus, ToMV, Runia, 1994a).

Hydrogen peroxide and activated peroxygens. The effective dose to control microorganisms ranges from 12.3 mg l⁻¹ hydrogen peroxide combined with 8 mg l⁻¹ peroxyacetic acid for control of algae (Choppakatla, 2009) to 185 mg l⁻¹ hydrogen peroxide plus 120 mg l⁻¹ peroxyacetic acid with 1-minute contact time to control *Phytophthora* sp. (Steddom and Pruett, 2012).

Copper. A dose between 2 and 4 mg l⁻¹ can effectively control several microorganisms (Raudales et al., 2014). However, an extended contact time of several hours is often required for control. Greenhouses and nursery growers typically apply 1 mg Cu l⁻¹ from ionized copper to prevent algae buildup and control plant pathogens (Zheng et al., 2005).

Silver. Effective doses to control plant pathogens with silver nitrate range from 0.07 mg l⁻¹ for conidia of *F. oxysporum* f. sp. *lycopersici* to 0.50 mg l⁻¹ for conidia of *F. oxysporum* f. sp. *dianthi* (Slade and Pegg, 1993).

Bromine. Reported effective doses of this compound range between 25 and 60 mg l⁻¹ (Raudales et al., 2014).

- **Physical treatments:**

Membrane filters with small pore size (<10 µm) are suitable for removal of microorganisms from water (Ehret et al., 2001; Stewart- Wade, 2011; Ufer et al., 2008; Van Os, 2010). Depending on pore size, membrane filters can be classified as micro- (0.1–10 µm), ultra- (0.1–0.002 µm), nano- (0.0005–0.002 µm) filtration, or reverse osmosis (<0.0005 µm) (Van der Bruggen et al., 2003). Microbial propagules differ in size depending on the type of organism and the life stage, which should be considered when selecting between filtration systems (Raudales et al., 2014). For example, within the genus *Phytophthora*, the length of sporangia ranges from 10 µm (*P. katsurae*) up to 171 µm (*P. erythrosetpica* var. *erythrosetpica*) (Erwin and Ribeiro, 1996), and that of zoospores and mycelia between 5 and 10 µm (Erwin and Ribeiro, 1996). Bacteria range between 0.6 and 3.5 µm in diameter (Agrios, 2005). Viruses vary in size from 0.03 to 2 µm long (Gergerich and Dolja, 2006).

Ultraviolet radiation. The effective range of UVC radiation, which includes the peak of UV absorbance by DNA (Hijnen et al., 2006), to control plant pathogens was between 28 mJ cm⁻² for *F. oxysporum* f. sp. *lycopersici* (Runia, 1995) and 850 mJ cm⁻² for *Alternaria zinniae* (Mebalds et al., 1995) (Table 9). The suggested water treatment for growers to control most pathogens is 250 mJ cm⁻² (Runia, 1994b, 1995).

Heat treatment is applied by passing water through a series of heat exchangers until the target temperature. After the required contact time is provided, heat is recovered and the solution is cooled before application (Raudales et al., 2014). Effective temperatures to control plant pathogens range from 40°C for 90 s for *Phytophthora cryptogea* zoospores (Runia and Amsing, 2001) to 95°C for 30 s for *Agrobacterium tumefaciens* (Poncet et al., 2001).

- **Ecological treatments:**

Slow sand filtration can remove from contaminated water a high percentage of some plant pathogens (e.g., *Phytophthora*, *Fusarium*, bacteria, nematodes, and viruses) by a combination of biological, physical and chemical processes. They are composed of a fine round sand (<0.3 mm diameter) upper layer (>1.4 m deep), followed by gravel (0.5 m deep), and underdrainage perforated pipes that will drain the water to a reservoir (Ellis and Wood, 1985; Raudales et al., 2015). Water flows slowly through these layers at a rate between 100 and 300 L m⁻² h⁻¹ (Wohanka, 1995). The upper layer of the sand bed contains a complex microbial community, known as Schmutzdecke, which must be always covered with water to maintain its biological activity (Ellis and Wood, 1985; Weller et al., 2002; Gimbel et al., 2007). The efficacy of this treatment may be not complete (Raudales et al., 2015). Importantly, the physico-chemical characteristics of the treated water, which remain unaltered after the treatment, may affect the activity of the Schmutzdecke.

Biosurfactants are biofungicides (*rhamnolipid*, *nitrapyrin*) produced from the aerobic fermentation of *Pseudomonas aeruginosa* (Stanghellini and Miller, 1997; US-EPA, 2013b; Raudales et al., 2015). They reduce oomycete survival and disease incidence (Pagliaccia et al., 2007). However, they can cause phytotoxicity when applied in overhead and ebb and flow irrigation (Nielsen et al., 2006).

Constructed wetlands remove pathogens most likely through complex and interacting physicochemical and biological processes within the wetland ecosystem (Headley et al., 2005; Huett, 2002). These infrastructures are highly efficient in removing not only plant pathogens but also water contaminants including nitrogen and phosphorus. Constructed wetlands are an active and emerging area of research (Raudales et al., 2015).

B. Risk factors

Table 1. Points of application of measures

RROs	Place of production at origin		Processing at origin	Export	Transport	Entry point	Destination
	Pre-harvest	Harvest	Post-harvest			Import	
Chemical control	x						
Filtration	x						
Heat	x						
UV radiation	x						
Ecological methods	x						

C. Parameters to consider regarding effectiveness of the RRO

Parameters related to nature of the chemical compound
Efficacy of the compound / mixture chosen
Duration of the treatment
Parameters related to filter pore size
Relative size of the target pathogen and the pore size
Parameters related to water quality
Impact of the concentration of suspended solids on the effectiveness of the treatment
Impact of the presence of ions on the effectiveness of the treatment
Impact of pH on the efficacy of the treatment
Impact of temperature on the effectiveness and/or duration of the treatment
Parameters related to the target pest
Susceptibility of the target species (fungi, oomycetes, bacteria, fungi, , others)
Relative susceptibility of the different stages (e.g. spore versus mycelia) of the target species
Parameters related to the host plant
Crop phytotoxicity
Parameters linked to crop production
Use of recycled water in crop production including use of exceeding irrigation water.

D. Applicability / feasibility of the RRO

The use of irrigation water from non-contaminated sources, other than rivers or ditches, may present technical difficulties of implementation depending on its availability.

In order to prevent the spread of *Ralstonia solanacearum* in potato and in other susceptible host plants, the provisions of the Council Directive 98/57/EC¹ on the control of this bacterium include in Annex VI 4.2 (bb) the ban of the use of contaminated water for irrigation and spraying. Following the provisions of this directive, the use of contaminated water may be permitted only under official control where officially approved techniques are employed for its decontamination.

The effectiveness of chemical treatments depends on the target organism, and the dose with respect to concentration or intensity and contact time (Ehret et al., 2001; Lane, 2004; Runia, 1995; Stewart-Wade, 2011; Van Os, 2010).

Detrimental phytotoxic effects of chemical control on plants have been reported, even for concentrations lower than those required to control some pathogens. Therefore, either longer contact with a lower concentration or removal of active substance before reuse (e.g., using activated carbon, Suidan et al., 1980) may have to be implemented.

Water quality parameters, such as the concentration of suspended solids, presence of ions, pH, and temperature affect disinfection strength of water treatments (Copes et al., 2004; Huang et al., 2011). For instance, chlorine efficacy decreases rapidly at high pH, or in the presence of organic and nitrogen contaminants (Raudales et al., 2014). Membrane filters can be clogged by suspended solids (sand, silt, organic matter), chemical precipitates, bacteria and algae (Moens and Hendrickx, 1992; Yiaosumi et al., 2005). As a consequence, pre-filtration of suspended solids is essential before membrane filtration to prevent membrane clogging (Van der Bruggen et al., 2003) and may also increase the effectiveness of any further chemical treatment.

¹ Council Directive 98/57/EC of 20 July 1998 on the control of *Ralstonia solanacearum* (Smith) Yabuuchi et al. Amended by Commission Directive 2006/63/CE of 14 July 2006.

For some chemical treatments, human and environmental issues have to be considered. For instance, chlorination of organic compounds can result in toxic by products such as trihalomethanes and haloacetic acids, which can be hazardous for human health (Deborde and von Gunten, 2008; Bull et al., 1990). Ozone is an atmospheric pollutant for human health and systems must be designed to avoid off-gassing of concentrated ozone into the work environment.

E. Other RROs that may lead to similar effects

Any RRO aimed at reducing the pest (pathogenic microorganisms) prevalence at origin may have similar effects.

F. Combinations of RROs that include this RRO

Application of one water treatment technology may not control resistant pathogens without risk of phytotoxicity or excess cost, and will not control potential sources of inoculum other than irrigation water (Raudales et al., 2014). Therefore, this RRO should be applied in combination with other RROs within the IPM philosophy, including the use of resistant cultivars, certified plant material or pesticide applications when needed, together with good cropping practices such as monitoring of water quality and matching irrigation practices with plant water needs.

This RRO may be part of requirements to grow pest-free plants in isolation (information sheet 1.01), or to establish pest-free places of production or pest-free production sites.

The effectiveness of this RRO should be checked by regular testing of water.

G. Conclusion

Synoptic table for the RRO

Target	Area of application	Expected effect	Main technical limitations of use	RROs with similar effects / most often in combinations
Pathogens	place of production (open or protected cultivation)	Reduce the probability of entry acting on the association of the pest at origin	Water quality Phytotoxicity Regulatory issues (availability of chemical compounds)	Other cultural practices intended to lower the pest load at place of production as: pesticide treatment, crop rotation, control of weeds hosting the pest.

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